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Communicative Competence Formation of a Teacher in the Field of Extended Education

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Abstract

The educator in extended education by virtue of the characteristics of his profession; forms the tastes, attitudes, beliefs and ideals of students. The formation of communicative competence is a key component of the professional look of the modern teacher of continuing education. The communicative competence of an additional education teacher is: 1) the ability to make a socio-psychological forecast of a communicative situation in which a communicative interaction is to be; 2) the ability to program the communication process, relying on the originality of the communicative situation, thirdly, the ability to manage communication processes in a communicative situation.

Based on the foregoing, the purpose of the study is the theoretical justification and experimental verification of the content, a complex of forms and methods that ensure the effective formation of communicative competence in future teachers of further education. Research methods: diagnostic testing using the methods of "Communicative and organizational inclinations", the questionnaire "Measuring communicative and social competence", "Assessing the level of conflict of personality", observation, questionnaire, pedagogical experiment; - data processing methods: qualitative and quantitative analysis, paired t-student test, G-test signs, Wilcoxon t-test. The experimental base was the Institute of Psychology and Education of the Kazan Federal University.

At the formative stage of the study, we implemented a program to form the communicative competence of future additional education teachers. The use of Student's t-test showed that after the experiment, there are significant differences in all the studied qualities.

Keywords: communicative competence, teacher in extended education, professional competence, professional skills, modern day pedagogue.

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Introduction

Nowadays education in our society is positioned as one of the many service sectors, and therefore, a special approach is required to the competencies of teachers. The rapid changes in modern life require a new understanding of their role in the pedagogical process from educators. In the conditions of intensive changes that occur in the education system, the teacher's activities are becoming more multifaceted, and the requirements for the qualitative characteristics of specialists in this field are increasing. Moreover, changes in the teacher's activities are performed through such aspects as inclusion of education among the priority national projects in order to systematically improve domestic education and move from the position of "catching up" to the real competitiveness of Russian education with world leaders in this field.

Continuing professional development of teachers has a direct impact on improving the quality of education, the development of creativity and talent of children, the formation of the personality as a whole, which is the main task of institutions of extended education. Understanding the issue of improving the system of teachers' training and retraining follows from an understanding of the need for changes in professional value orientations.

Today, it is important for the teacher to be able to organize the educational process, not only with the help of ideas of personal development education, but also to possess modern knowledge of the methodology and new technologies; skills of research activities, be able to use innovations in pedagogical design based on the analysis and introspection of professional activity.

The organization of the educational environment, which will contribute to the development of the child's personality, can be put forward as the main task of the institution of extended education. In this regard, there is a need for the use of certain professional standards that should be applied to the teacher of extended education. One of the main components necessary both for the general cultural development of the future teacher of extended education, and for his aesthetic and pedagogical activity is the communicative component. The idea of developing competencies is one of the key ideas in the modernization of education. The professional competence of the teacher in the system of advanced training is not limited to a set of knowledge and skills, but is determined by the effectiveness of their use in real educational practice. To have competencies means to be able to activate existing knowledge, experience, one's mood and will to solve a problem in specific circumstances. One of the key competencies of a teacher is communicative competence - this is a professionally significant, personal quality of a specialist, which is formed in the process of self-development. In addition to the sphere of interpersonal communication, here by communication we mean the whole complex of social interactions, during which stable ideas about the

world are formed. In this case, the goal should not be comprehension of the truth, but the formation of confidential interaction, during which the idea of reality is determined by a socially significant subject. This is especially important in extended education. A survey among students shows that children attend hobby groups and clubs in many ways not so much to learn something, but to communicate with a teacher.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is the theoretical justification and experimental verification of the content, the complex of forms and methods that ensure the effective formation of communicative competence in future teachers of extended education.

Literature review

Communicative component includes expressive and emotional interaction with other children, speech activity, performing activity, education and formation of children's joys of communication, empathy, and pleasure from communication, the ability to hold the audience, to tell children about the subject enthusiastically and vividly. The formation of teachers' communicative competence was reviewed by such famous researchers as Kazarinova et al. (2011), Klyueva (2003), Zhukov et al. (2015). The analysis of the communicative and pedagogical skills most often reflected in the works of Bodalev (1996), Kan-Kalik and Nikandrov (1990), Konev (1998) and Markov (2003).

The theoretical foundations of students' communicative competence are determined by researchers Vyatutnev (2007), Zimnaya (2013), Kuzmina and Sokolov (2007), Leontiev (2005), Leontiev (2000), and Mazo (2000) as the ability to carry out speech activity, the implementation of communicative behavior based on a system of components: motivational (speech behavior), cognitive (knowledge), and operational (overcoming the contradictions prescribed by the content of training).

Zimnaya (2013) explains the concept of "competence" as "an actual, formed quality of a person based on knowledge, intellectually and personality-determined social and professional trait of a person, his personality quality" (p. 12). Moreover, the term "competence" is defined as "internal, potential, hidden psychological neoplasms (knowledge, perceptions, programs of action), which are then revealed in a person's competencies" (p. 15).

As part of our study, we adhered to the definition of Zhukov et al. (2015), who claims that communicative competence is a psychological characteristic of an individual as a person, which manifests itself in communication and the ability to establish and maintain the necessary contacts with people. In this regard,

it was concluded that the formation of communicative competence can be judged by the formation of the following components: situation understanding, emotional stability, self-presentation ability, confidence, socio-psychological competence, communicative and organizational inclinations.

Despite the fact that the problem of forming the communicative competence of the extended education teacher is quite acute in our time, there are no separate studies and developments regarding the formation of the communicative competence of a future extended education teacher.

The relevance of this study first of all lies in the fact that the formation of communicative competence is a key component of the professional look of the modern day teacher of extended education.

In terms of content communicative competence should include not only a set of skills of verbal and non-verbal professional and cultural communication, but also the basics of creating and correcting one's image - an image that largely determines the mood for mutual understanding and trust in a teacher.

Methodology

Within the research the following methods were used:

- theoretical: the study and analysis of pedagogical, psychological and social literature on the research problem, systematization and generalization;
- empirical: diagnostic assessment using the methods of "Communicative and organizational inclinations", the questionnaire "Measuring communicative and social competence", "Assessing the level of conflict of personality", monitoring, surveying, pedagogical experiment;
- data processing methods: qualitative and quantitative analysis, paired t-student test, G-criterion of signs, Wilcoxon t-test.

The Institute of Psychology and Education of Kazan Federal University became the experimental base. The experiment was attended by 50 students from the academic program "Extended education and English language".

Results

1. At the first stage, the ascertaining experiment was organized with the primary diagnosis of the studied indicators. We used such methods as the "Scale for assessing the communicative and organizational inclinations of university students", "Assessment the level of personality conflict" (Andreev, 1995) and

methods for measuring communicative and social competence (Kazarinova et al., 2011). Let us identify the features of used methods.

1.1 Questionnaire “Communicative and organizational abilities”.

According to the results of individual’s answers, it becomes possible to identify the qualitative features of his communicative and organizational abilities. In general, the procedure is as follows: for each question (40 questions of the questionnaire), you should answer “yes” or “no”. The result is calculated with the answer key for each section of the methodology, then the estimated coefficients are calculated separately for communicative and organizational abilities according to the formula: $K = 0.05 * C$, where K is the estimated coefficient; C is the number of responses that match the key. Estimated coefficients can vary from 0 to 1. Indicators that are closer to 1 indicate a high level of communicative and organizational skills, close to 0 indicate a low level.

1.2 “Assessment the level of personality conflict”.

When answering questions (14 questions), it is proposed to choose one answer out of three. In accordance with the scores, the level of conflict of the individual is determined. It ranges from 14-17 (very low) to 39-42 (very high).

1.3 Technique “Measuring communicative and social competence”.

Teachers' ideas about their communicative skills in interpersonal communication allow us to evaluate the following scales: image, verbal competence, ego-competence, operational social competence, socio-psychological competence, communicative competence. At the same time, the core in the questionnaire is the scale of communicative competence. Out of 15 proposed scales we selected 8 that are most consistent with the objectives of our study:

1. situation understanding;
2. emotional stability;
3. self-presentation ability;
4. socio-psychological competence;
5. communicative competence;

6. confidence;
7. stability of personal relations;
8. communicative and personal potential.

The respondent is awarded 1 point if the answer matches the key. On each scale it is possible to score from 0 to 6 points. Thus, on 8 scales the most reflective is the level of social-communicative competence where the respondent can gain from 0 to 48 points.

2. At the formative stage we have developed and tested a program “Let`s communicate” in order to form the communicative competence of future extended education teachers, which was based on such methods and forms of communicative competence formation as working in groups, participating in dialogue and discussion, playing roles, group games and exercises, social-psychological training, communicative-situational tasks, "business theatre". The formative stage of the experimental work was aimed at creating an effective program for the formation of the communicative competence of future extended education teachers using the forms and methods of forming communicative competence that were identified above.

Designed program is an effective means of developing the communicative competence of future teachers of extended education which helps to remove psychological barriers that impede normal communication, builds the ability to understand and accept another person, the ability to listen and defend one's point of view, as it is a kind of platform for future teachers to master the process of forming the interpersonal relationships in conditions that are as close as possible to real ones.

It is important for future teachers of extended education to provide an opportunity to think, reason about any problems that arise within the team and society, evaluate and discuss ways of solving, so that they can independently engage in an active dialogue, and can learn can learn the features of cooperation and co-creation in practice.

When designing the program for the formation of communicative competence “I can communicate” we relied on the provisions of Russian and foreign psychology.

The main aim of this program is to form the communicative competence of future teachers of extended education.

The objectives of the program are the following:

- systematization of knowledge about communicative competence and its specifics about etiquette of communication and non-verbal means of communication;
- formation of students' ideas about communicative competence as a cultural value and an instrument for organizing any professional activity;
- formation of the readiness of a graduate to use communicative competence in practice;
- formation of readiness of a graduate to participate in verbal and non-verbal communication.

The content of a program reveals the main aspects of the formation of the communicative competence of future teachers of extended education: formation of position in interaction; interpersonal interaction; creating an atmosphere of trust and openness; reflective perception of communication situations and communication partners; non-verbal communication and the problem of emotional expression; verbal communication, listening, instructive and destructive forms of influence on the interlocutor, patterns that increase mutual understanding, personal charm and communication; interference in communication; communication in the conflict, the main forms of behavior in the conflict, conflict resolution; strategy for cooperation in conflict, accommodation of interests.

When implementing the program we tried to create the following situations for the participants in which:

- the feeling of fear of public speaking is removed;
- the willingness to accept and provide assistance is developing;
- the ability to communicative and organizational activities are revealed;
- initiative and activity is developed;
- the ability to analyze their actions and current events and the awareness of their attitude to the world are developed;
- a positive attitude is being formed towards one's and others' work, as well as the ability to take responsibility for one's actions and those of others;
- the ability to listen to others is developed;

- a sense of empathy and compassion for another people are developed;
- the skill of behavior in conflict situations is developed;
- contacts are being established in the group and intergroup relations.

The main tasks of a teacher in his work aimed at forming the communicative competence:

- to encourage students to manifest relationships, attitudes, emotional reactions, and to discuss, analyze, and review topics proposed;
- to create the conditions within a group for the full disclosure of students` problems and emotions in an atmosphere of mutual acceptance, security, support and protection;
- to develop and maintain the certain standards in the group, the manifestation of flexibility when selecting the exposure techniques.

The program for forming the communicative competence of future teachers of extended education “I can communicate” was carried out for 5 months and contained 25 lessons. This number of classes can be considered sufficient to achieve the goals in the formation of the communicative competence of future extended education teachers. Each lesson consisted of 4-5 different methods and techniques. Classes begin with greetings by the participants of each other, then the main part of the lesson that is relevant to the topic, and at the end - summing up and reflection.

The classes are structured in such way that each participant “experiences” various situations, determines his communication skills, ability to support, to recognize the merits of another person, to convince, to be able to defend his position, to listen and hear another one, and also understand and accept another person, empathize and be compassionate, be able to effectively interact in a conflict, build relationships with other participants. Everyone recognizes himself as a communication partner, discovers the most diverse aspects of the personality: those that help to establish contact and those that interfere with this.

The integrative approach to conducting classes on the formation of the communicative competence of future teachers of extended education made it possible to most thoroughly consider issues related to interaction in society and to give participants valuable experience in researching both their own personality, their beliefs, habits, and interpersonal interaction skills. Seeing yourself through the eyes of others, living together difficult life situations modeled in the classroom, reacting and expressing your feelings, discussing current issues - all this was possible during the implementation of the program.

During the implementation of the program for forming the communicative competence “I can communicate”, the following features were noted: from a state of suspicion and closeness through research interest the confidence gradually appeared as well as the desire to establish relationships with other participants and the presenter. At the first stage of work sometimes we noted the rivalry and a desire for power, and sometimes participants fought for the leadership. On the last day, the need for attachment came to the fore: participants established a close emotional connection with each other.

3. At the control stage of the experiment we analyzed the obtained results and carried out the statistical and mathematical data processing.

Discussions

While tracking the dynamics of the development of the communicative competence of future teachers of extended education at the control stage, we found out that the level of communicative competence of the group became higher than the indicators of the ascertaining stage of the experiment.

The communicative abilities of low level at the control stage were not detected (14.28%), which indicates the changes by 38.1%, 14.28% of respondents have a level below average, 19.04% at an average level, a high level increased from 4.76% to 23.8% (changes by 19.04%), the highest level increased from 9.52% to 28.57% (changes by 19.05%).

The low level of organizational inclinations in the experimental group decreased from 66.66% to 28.57%, the level below the average increased from 9.52% to 28.57% (changes by 19.05%), the average level decreased from 9.52% to 4.76% (changes by 4.76%), the high level increased from 4.76% to 23.8% (changes by 19.04%), the highest level of the group increased from 9.52% to 14.28% (change of 4.76%).

As a result of studying the level of conflict of future teachers of extended education the following trends were revealed: the arithmetic average for the group of respondents was 25.2, which indicates that the level of conflict in the group of respondents is slightly lower than the average and that is 5.9 less than the indicator of the ascertaining experiment.

When tracking the dynamics of the development of the communicative competence of future teachers of extended education at the control stage we found out that the level of communicative competence of the group was significantly higher than the indicators of the ascertaining experiment. The use of Student's t-test showed that after the experiment there were significant differences in all studied qualities. The use of the G-test of signs` criterion and t-test of Wilcoxon confirmed a shift towards improvement in average

indicators. The obtained results of the study of communicative inclinations by the t-test indicate the presence of significant differences. In other words, the forms and methods used in working with students - future teachers of extended education under the program "Let`s communicate" are highly effective in the formation of communicative inclinations. To test the effectiveness of the "Let`s communicate" program in reducing personality conflicts we conducted a statistical analysis using the Wilcoxon test for related samples. Unlike the paired Student t-test, this technique does not require verification of the normal distribution of the sample.

The Wilcoxon T-test is used to assess the differences between two series of measurements that are performed for the same set of respondents, but under different conditions or at different times. This test is able to identify the direction and severity of changes and shows whether the indicators are more shifted in one direction than in the other. According to the calculations, it was proved that the level of indicators of personality conflict before and after the formative stage of the experiment at the ascertaining and control stages is different.

Based on the results obtained using the three methods it can be concluded that the level of communication skills of future extended education teachers is at an average level, the majority of respondents are characterized by high and higher levels of communication and organizational inclinations, the manifestation of initiative in activities is not underestimated, students do not avoid making independent decisions.

The average level of communicative and organizational inclinations is manifested in the fact that respondents seek contacts, defend their opinions, and plan work.

The level of conflict is below the average, and this fact indicates that in the analysis and assessment of the situation of contradiction, future teachers of extended education inconsistently show an adequate understanding of the conflict; the flexibility of the mind allows you to objectively perceive the situation as conflict or non-conflict and to find optimal models for further conflict behavior; they prefer not to enter into any conflicts, they leave disputes, most often they choose to adapt in the conflict situations.

Conclusion

Thus, analyzing and comparing the results of the ascertaining and control stages of the experimental work we can say that the program that was developed to form the communicative competence of future extended education teachers is really effective, since the results showed positive dynamics and effectiveness of this program, which indicates the effectiveness of the work. We can conclude that the program we developed

for the formation of communicative competence, which is based on the forms and methods that we have identified above, plays an important role in shaping the communicative competence of future teachers of extended education.

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